

Germplasm improvement

Genetic resources

ITS1 sequences of nuclear ribosome DNA in rice species from China and their phylogenetic implications

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This study assessed the capability of using internal transcribed spacer (ITS1) sequences for reconstructing the phylogeny of rice species from China. Three accessions of wild and two accessions of cultivated rice were used (Table 1). Total DNA was extracted from leaf samples following the procedures described by Tai and Tanksley (1990). Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) amplifications were performed in 50 μ L volumes containing 100 ng DNA template and 2.5 μ L Taq polymerase. A PE-

480 thermal cycler was used under the following conditions: 35 cycles of 94 °C for 1 min, 57 °C for 1 min, and 72 °C for 1 min. PCR-amplified DNA products were recovered, complemented, and then cloned into the vector pUC 118 with standard protocols. Sequencing of ITS1 was conducted on an ABI 373A automated sequencer using a TaqDye Primer Cycle Sequencing Kit (ABI). The ITS1 sequences of the five taxa together with a published rice sequence (Takaiwa et al 1985) were aligned with the Clustal V program. The data matrix was analyzed using UPGMA with Jukes-Cantor distance and Neighbor-Joining with Kimura 2-parameter distance of the MEGA version 1.02 (Kura et al 1993).

The ITS1 sequences of the three wild species and two subspecies of cultivated rice showed diversity in size from 193 bp (*Oryza rufipogon*) to 218 bp (*O. granulata*) (Table 2). To date, these ITS1 sequences were the shortest

Table 2. Size and G+C content of ITS1 sequences of six rice accessions.

Accession number	Taxon	Sequence size (bp)	G+C content (%)
1	<i>O. rufipogon</i>	193	72.7
2	<i>O. sativa</i> ssp. <i>indica</i>	194	72.3
3	<i>O. sativa</i> ssp. <i>japonica</i>	194	72.3
4	<i>O. sativa</i> ^a	194	72.3
5	<i>O. officinalis</i>	194	72.3
6	<i>O. granulata</i>	218	69.3

^a From Takaiwa et al 1985. Plant Mol. Biol. 4:355-364.

among angiosperms studied, except for *O. granulata*. Percentage of G+C contents of the five taxa ranged from 69.3% to 72.2% (Table 2), and the G+C contents are the highest in angiosperms examined so far. The alignment of the ITS1 sequences, using *O. rufipogon* as a standard, yielded 223 characters with 116 (52.0%) identical sites for all sequences and 107 (47.9%) variable sites, of which 28 sites (12.6%) were phylogenetically informative.

Based on analysis of ITS1 sequences, this study suggests that *O. granulata* has a distant relationship with other *Oryza* species. Because the relationships of the rice species used in this study agree with those generated from other studies, ITS1 may be considered a useful tool for addressing phylogenetic questions in the genus *Oryza*. ■

Table 1. *Oryza* species included in this study,

Accession number	Taxon	Genome	Origin	Voucher specimen
1	<i>O. sativa</i> ssp. <i>indica</i>	AA	China	-
2	<i>O. sativa</i> ssp. <i>japonica</i>	AA	Yunnan, China	-
3	<i>O. rufipogon</i>	AA	Guangxi, China	Zhou Yi 940135
5	<i>O. officinalis</i>	CC	Hainan, China	Zhang Shou-zhou 940130
6	<i>O. granulata</i>	Diploid	Yunnan, China	Gao Li-zhi 940208

Quantitative trait locus analysis of trait variation among annual and perennial ecotypes of *Oryza rufipogon*

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Quantitative trait locus (QTL) analysis was conducted to study variation among annual and perennial ecotypes of *Oryza rufipogon*, the wild progenitor of rice. The 101 F₂ offspring analyzed resulted from a cross between a single

annual and a single perennial plant regenerated from seeds collected in Bangkok, Thailand. Each F₂ genotype was split into two clones grown on adjacent short-day plots at Mishima, Japan, during the summer of 1994, and traits measured (see table). Several measurements were combined to capture the tendency toward annuality or perenniality, such as the ratio of panicles to tillers (high in annuals and low in perennials). Broad-sense heritability of each trait was calculated using an

ANOVA model. Each genotype was scored for 40 molecular markers single and multiple regression was used to estimate the proportion of phenotypic variation. Genetic variation explained by markers was estimated by dividing the phenotypic R^2 by the broad-sense heritability of each trait.

Broad-sense heritability of traits ranged from 0.81 to 0.37. Negative genetic correlations were found between most measures of fertility and vegetative persistence. Single QTL explained up to 27% of the phenotypic variation in the traits examined (see table). Multiple regressions explained from 7 to 38% of the phenotypic and from 18 to 62% of the genotypic variation in each trait. Some QTL appear to explain significant proportions of variation in several traits, suggesting pleiotropic effects. Marker G1184Ca is apparently linked to a QTL controlling the proportion of tillers that flower while having a negative pleiotropic effect on vegetative persistence. If this QTL is confirmed in further studies, it will represent a genetic locus that underlies the life history trade-off between reproduction and survival.

Our results contrast with recent QTL studies which have found chromosomal regions controlling large fractions of the phenotypic variation. We found only one case in which more

Single and multiple regressions of markers on traits. Underlined traits are those for which the annual ecotype expresses larger values (see references in Morishima et al 1992, Oxford Surv. Evol. Biol. 8:135-184).

Trait	Marker	Chromosome	$R^2_p^a$	$R^2_g^b$
Heading date	G1184Ca	1	0.135	0.175
	G1082	10	0.068	0.089
	Multiple regression		0.180	0.234
Anther length	RZ58	2	0.108	0.133
	G200	6	0.105	0.129
	G127	10	0.085	0.105
	G181	11	0.080	0.099
	Multiple regression		0.383	0.473
Height	C86	1	0.091	0.168
	G1184Ca	1	0.097	0.179
	C342	6	0.079	0.146
	G56	8	0.071	0.131
<u>Panicles tiller⁻¹</u>	Multiple regression		0.255	0.472
	G1184Ca	1	0.271	0.553
	RZ58	2	0.142	0.290
Panicle length	Multiple regression		0.304	0.620
	G1184Ca	1	0.062	0.124
	C196	2	0.118	0.235
	G1085	9	0.078	0.156
Spikelets panicle ⁻¹	Multiple regression		0.246	0.492
	G56	8	0.060	0.110
	C596	7	0.062	0.114
Regeneration index	Multiple regression		0.102	0.189
	G1082	10	0.066	0.179
Postharvest tillers/ preharvest tillers	G1184Ca	1	0.086	0.210
	C86	1	0.064	0.156
	C397	9	0.070	0.170
	C196	2	0.087	0.212
	Multiple regression		0.253	0.616
<u>Postharvest panicles/ postharvest tillers</u>	G1184Ca	1	0.168	0.271

^a R^2_p = phenotypic R^2 . ^b R^2_g = genotypic R^2 , calculated as $R^2_p \times H^2$.

than 25% of the phenotypic variation in a trait is explained by a single marker. Ecological adjustments that contribute to intraspecific annual \times perennial dif-

ferentiation in *O. rufipogon*, therefore, may be more polygenic than species differences examined in previous studies. ■

Determination of chromosome numbers of wild *Oryza* species conserved in the International Rice Genebank at IRRI

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To date, more than 3,000 wild rice accessions, representing 21 species of *Oryza* and 11 related genera, are being conserved in the International Rice Genebank (IRG) at IRRI. The chromosome number of each conserved accession of different *Oryza* species, which should be part of the passport data, is essential to facilitate characterization and species identification.

Number of accessions in each *Oryza* species for which chromosome number has been determined.

Species	Accessions (no.)	Chromosome number	Source
<i>O. australiensis</i>	17	24	Australia
<i>O. barthii</i>	141	24	Africa
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	11	24	Africa
<i>O. eichingeri</i> (diploid)	14	24	Africa, Asia
<i>O. glumaepatula</i>	37	24	South America
<i>O. granulata</i>	18	24	Asia
<i>O. longistaminata</i>	4	24	Africa
<i>O. meridionalis</i>	35	24	Australia
<i>O. nivara</i>	215	24	Asia
<i>O. officinalis</i> (diploid)	136	24	Asia
<i>O. rufipogon</i>	31	24	Asia
<i>O. sativa</i> f. <i>spontanea</i>	1	24	Indonesia
<i>O. alta</i>	6	48	South America
<i>O. eichingeri</i> (tetraploid)	4	48	Uganda, Sri Lanka
<i>O. grandiglumis</i>	9	48	South America
<i>O. longiglumis</i>	5	48	Indonesia, Papua New Guinea
<i>O. minuta</i>	48	48	Philippines
<i>O. officinalis</i> (tetraploid)	2	48	India
<i>O. punctata</i> (tetraploid)	1	48	Kenya
<i>O. ridleii</i>	7	48	Southeast Asia
Total	742		